

VO₂ based Thermochromic Coatings for Smart window Application

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Abstract

Thermochromic (TC) smart coatings are promising for modulating solar radiations. A TC window can be used to automatically control the temperature inside the buildings. Vanadium dioxide (VO₂) was found to be a potent material for technology with a reversible phase transition from monoclinic to tetragonal in somewhat near ambient temperature. However, its use is constrained by low visible transmission (T_{lum}) and high transition temperature (T_c). We achieved a favorable combination of lower T_c , higher ΔT_{sol} and higher T_{lum} by a controlled co-doping of VO₂ with tungsten (W). We adopted a solution processing method that has the advantage of lower cost and easier processability compared to typical vacuum techniques. The precursor is prepared from the V₂O₅ powder and spin coated on the quartz substrate followed by one step annealing at 550^oC in Ar. flow. The major aim of the work is to reduce the transition temperature near 24-30^oC and modulate the NIR throughput for window application. Annealing conditions play major role for creating monoclinic VO₂ phase. The produced monoclinic phase shows 43% contrast at 2500 nm with a 25% T_c reduction which is comparable to the other research works.

Keywords : VO₂, solar modulation, co-doping , Thermochromism

References

1. Wang et.al Mg/W-codoped vanadium dioxide thin films with enhanced visible transmittance and low phase transition temperature *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2015, 3, 6771